

Mechanism of radioprotection by 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan[†]

S. N. Upadhyay

Radiation Biology Department, Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences, Brig. S. K. Mazumdar Marg, Delhi-110 054, India

Manuscript received 4 January 2002, revised 19 September 2002, accepted 12 December 2002

Present review summarizes the radiochemical mechanism of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan (5HTP) for its radioprotection aspect. The structural and functional aspects of 5HTP that are responsible for radioprotection in different organs have been reported. The constituents of these organs in turn interact with 5HTP and thereby accessibility of free radicals to these organs is minimized. Moreover, the nucleolar constituents like DNA and nucleohistone also interact with 5HTP. That is also partially responsible for radioprotection. 5HTP has the capability to combat different physiological aberration syndromes.

5-Hydroxy-L-tryptophan (5-HTP) in combination with β -aminoethylisothiuronium bromide hydrobromide (AET) in a concentration ratio of 90.82 : 14.23 (μ M) has been reported to give radioprotection to different biological systems in the dose range 4–12 Gy. The dose rate was found to be 0.004–0.04 Gy/s for ⁶⁰Co-gamma rays^{1–7}. For 5-HTP, LD₅₀₍₃₀₎ value is 610 mg/kg⁸. While AET has been reported to be toxic⁹, 5-HTP is not¹⁰. Moreover, radiation protection mechanism offered by AET is known^{11–13} whereas that for 5-HTP is scanty.

Radiochemical mechanism

5-HTP (m.p. 270°; solubility 1 g/100 ml in water at 37°) shows absorption maximum at 207 and 275 nm and a shoulder at 220 nm and fluorescence emission maximum being at 340 nm (E_m) when excited at 287 nm (E_m)¹². The functional groups responsible for absorption maximum and shoulder are pyrrole, $-\text{CH}_2-\text{CH}(\text{NH}_2)-\text{COOH}$ and indole groups¹⁴. The assignments of IR spectral bands of 5-HTP in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states are shown in Table 1.

The transient radiolytic products of water are

The G -values have been reported as $G(\text{OH}^\bullet) = G(e_{\text{aq}}^-) = G(\text{H}_3\text{O}^+) = 2.7$ and $G(\text{H}^\bullet) = 0.6$. In presence of oxygen¹⁵, $G(-\text{TRP}) = 4$ and diffusion coefficient values¹⁶ are of the order of $10^{-9} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$.

When 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan is irradiated in aqueous solution the absorbed energy is distributed approximately in proportion to the mass ratios of constituents¹⁷. The hydrated electron will react with amino acids¹⁸ as

Hydroxyl radicals will be scavenged by COOH group (ionized form) effectively, and H^+ ions will protonate the amino groups. Deamination at the alpha-carbon atom position is a relatively easier process. But its intensity is not high, $G(\text{NH}_3)$ 0.5 in both evacuated and oxygenated solutions of tryptophan¹⁹. The lone-pair of electrons present with in-

Table 1. Infrared characteristics of 5-hydroxy-L-tryptophan in the unirradiated and gamma-irradiated states*

ν_{max} cm^{-1}	Unirradiated	Gamma-irradiated	Assignment
3400	83.0 Doublet	75.7 No doublet	Decarboxylation from side-chain. Dissociation of zwitterion. Deamination is only possible when the amino groups are from OH-stretch
2900		74.0	
2850		73.0	
1500		70.0	
1200		70.0	
1150	75.0	83.0	C–OH linkage of
1100		68.0	5-hydroxyl group of
1050	74.0	86.0	5HTP. Intermolecular
1000	55.0	65.0	hydrogen bonding. This is disrupted upon gamma irradiation
980	78.0	87.0	The adjacent two free
930	79.0	90.0	hydrogen atoms in the
850	60.0	73.0	benzene ring have been shown

*Refs. 12, 21.

[†]Presented in the 33rd. Annual Conference of Society of Nuclear Medicine (India), Delhi, 2001.

dole nitrogen is also responsible for radioprotection²⁰. The formation of all the chromophoric groups of 5HTP and their quantity is dependent upon total dose and dose rate. The radiolytic decomposition of 5HTP has been reported by us^{12,21}. The radiosensitivity of other neutral radiolytic products²² of 5HTP for a dose of 100 Gy were in the following decreasing order : 5-hydroxyindole-2-acetic acid (5HI2AA) > 5-hydroxyindole-3-acetic acid (5HI3AA) > 5-hydroxyindole (5HI) > 5-hydroxytryptamine (5HT) > 5-hydroxy-l-tryptophan (5HTP). But the radioprotective efficacy was in the following decreasing order : 5HTP > 5HT > 5HI3AA > 5HI2AA > 5HI. Other radiolytic products of 5HTP reported²³ are 5-hydroxy-N-formylkineurenine and 5-hydroxykineurenine.

Interaction with nucleolar moiety

5HTP interacts with DNA and DNH²⁴. The modes of binding are by (i) electrostatic interaction, (ii) ion condensation, (iii) stacking and (iv) intercalation. The functional groups for binding are phenolic-OH, indole, -CH₂-CH-(NH₂)-COOH (side-chain), phosphate groups, phosphodiester bond, peptides, basic amino acids (e.g. lysine, arginine etc.) and chromophores like -C=C-C=N- and -C=C-C=O. The binding is dependent upon concentration, stereospecific attachment and nature of dissociation of these biopolymers in the solvents used. The accessibility of water-produced free radicals for radiation-induced damage to DNA and DNH is greatly hindered by their interaction with 5HTP. It is possible that 5HTP interaction with the bases (i.e. adenine, guanine, cytosine and thymine) of DNA and pentose sugar (Table 2).

Table 2.

Radioprotector	Constituent of lipid	Resultant compound
8-Hydroxy-l-tryptophan	+ 3-Phosphatidyl-ethanolamine	Amide formation
	+ Phosphatidyl-glycerol	i) Protonation of C=O groups by H ⁺ ions from COOH group ii) CONH formation
	+ Phosphatidic acid	i) Protonation of phosphate groups by COOH groups ii) CONH formation
	+ Lysolecithin	Amide formation
	+ Sphingomyelin	Neutralization of phosphate groups by H ⁺ ions from COOH group of 5HTP

Interaction with lipids²⁵

While incorporation, 5HTP interacts with the lipids present on the cell membrane. So the interaction must be with (i) phosphatidylethanolamine, (ii) phosphatidylglycerol, (iii) phosphatidic acid, (iv) lysolecithin and (v) sphingomyelin – the constituents of cell membrane. These are found in large quantities in brain, muscle and nerve tissues. Depending upon different biophysical parameters, like lyophilicity, membrane channel size, osmolarity, ionic strength, pH etc., the movement of 5HTP to different organs is decided (Table 2).

Biochemical pathway

As 5HTP is incorporated inside the body system, its biochemical pathway is also important²⁶ (Scheme 1).

Scheme 1. Biochemical pathway of 5HTP.

Physiological aspect

It will be evident that for different types of syndromes 5HTP is tolerated well. The different physiological aspects are given below.

(a) The efficacy and tolerability of 5HTP were conducted in 50 patients with primary fibromyalgia syndrome. All the clinical parameters studied were significantly improved by treatment with 5HTP. Mild and transient side-effects were reported²⁷.

(b) Oral administration of 5HTP causes decreased carbohydrate intake and weight-loss in obese patients²⁸.

(c) In diabetic patients orally administered 5HTP stimulates brain serotonin and normalizes eating behavior. In insulin-dependent diabetes mellitus patients 5HTP may be safely prescribed²⁸.

(d) 5HTP has been shown to improve depression, anxiety, insomnia and somatic pains in a variety of patient cohorts²⁹.

(e) 5HTP crosses blood-brain barrier and effectively increases serotonin level in CNS. So, therapeutic administration of 5HTP has been shown to be effective in treating a wide variety of conditions (depression, fibromyalgia, binge eating associated with chronic headache and insomnia)³⁰.

Acknowledgement

The author is thankful to Dr. H. C. Goel, Head, Radiation Biology Department and to Dr. T. Lazar Mathew, Ex-Director, Institute of Nuclear Medicine & Allied Sciences, for taking interest in this work.

References

1. A. Ghose, S. K. Basu, S. K. Ganguly, A. Bhatnagar and M. Mathur, *Strahlentherapie*, 1983, **159**, 772.
2. A. Ghose, S. K. Ganguly and J. Kaur, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1983, **44**, 178.
3. A. Ghose, S. K. Ganguly, J. Kaur and M. Mathur, *Radiobiol. Radiother.*, 1987, **28**, 477.
4. A. Ghose, S. K. Basu, A. Bhatnagar and R. C. Sarin, *Radiobiol. Radiother.*, 1987, **28**, 507.
5. S. K. Basu, M. N. Srinivasan, K. Chuttani and A. Ghose, *J. Radiat. Res.*, 1985, **26**, 395.
6. S. K. Basu, K. Chandra and K. Chuttani, *Acta Oncologica*, 1987, **26** (Fasc 3), 229.
7. M. N. Srinivasan, S. K. Basu and A. Ghose, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1985, **23**, 490.
8. S. N. Upadhyay, T. B. Dey and A. Ghose, *Indian J. Exp. Biol.*, 1996, **34**, 490.
9. W. A. Prutz, *Int. J. Radiat. Biol.*, 1989, **56**, 21.
10. B. Biber, Mc. Korrey, K. C. Grooves, L. Phan and R. Rosecrans, *Brain Res.*, 1989, **482**, 306.
11. S. N. Upadhyay, *Radiat. Protection Environ. Bull. Radiat. Protection*, 1998, **71**, 45.
12. S. N. Upadhyay, S. Singh and A. Ghose, *J. Indian. Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 681.
13. S. N. Upadhyay and S. N. Guha, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2001, **78**, 337.
14. S. N. Upadhyay, R. P. Singh, A. K. Gupta and A. Ghose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1988, **65**, 560.
15. R. V. Benasson, F. J. Land and T. G. Trasscott, "Excited States and Free Radicals in Biology and Medicine", Oxford University Press, Oxford, 1993.
16. W. Friedland, P. Jacob, H. G. Peretzka, M. Mazzagona and A. Hollenghi, *Radiat. Environ. Biophys.*, 1999, **38**, 39.
17. C. E. Klots in "The Fundamental Processes in Radiation Chemistry", ed. P. Auslos, Interscience, New York, 1968.
18. R. Montgomery, T. N. Conway and A. A. Spector, "Biochemistry – a Close Oriented Approach", C. V. Mosby Company, Philadelphia, 1990.
19. P. Alexander and D. Rosen, *Nature (London)*, 1960, **188**, 574.
20. C. Helene, *Excited States Chem. Biochem.*, 1977, **10**, 65.
21. S. N. Upadhyay, A. V. R. Warrior and A. Ghose, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1993, **70**, 763.
22. S. N. Upadhyay, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1994, **71**, 21.
23. A. Singh, M. J. Bell, G. N. Koroll, W. Kremers and H. Singh in "Oxygen and Oxyradicals in Chemistry and Biology", eds. M. A. J. Rodgers and E. L. Power, Academic, New York, 1981.
24. S. N. Upadhyay, R. P. Singh and A. Ghose, *J. Surface Sci. Technol.*, 1993, **9**, 67.
25. P. A. Mayess in "Harper's Biochemistry", eds. R. K. Murray, D. K. Grannar, P. A. Mayes and V. W. Rodwel, Prentice-Hall, New York, 1996.
26. A. Goodman and Gilman, "Synthesis and Inactivation of Serotonin in Pharmaceutical Basis of Therapeutics", ed. E. S. Bush and S. E. Mayer, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1991.
27. I. Caruso, P. S. Puttini, M. Carzolle and V. Azollini, *J. Int. Med. Res.*, 1990, **18**, 201.
28. C. Cangiano, A. Laviano, M. D. Ben, I. Preziosa, F. Angelico, A. Casino and F. Rossi-Fannelli, *Int. J. Obes. Related Metabolic Disorders*, 1998, **22**, 648.
29. J. H. Juhi, *Alternative Med. Rev.*, 1998, **3**, 367.
30. T. C. Birdshall, *Alternative Med. Rev.*, 1998, **3**, 271.